

Study on fast neutron multiplicity counting based on the reactor Monte Carlo Code RMC

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ABSTRACT

Traditional thermal-neutron multiplicity coincidence counting relies on ³He detectors and the thermal-neutron (n,p) reaction. Due to the scarcity of ³He, both homeland security and nuclear safeguards applications are actively seeking neutron detectors that can replace ³He tubes. Liquid scintillation detectors offer excellent (n,γ) discrimination capability, and they do not require neutron moderation; instead, they can directly detect fission neutrons emitted from nuclear materials. Fast-neutron detection provides significant advantages because it preserves and measures the intrinsic nanosecond time scale of spontaneous and induced fission neutrons, rather than the microsecond scale that results from neutron thermalization in thermal-neutron detectors. The neutron lifetime is shortened by up to three orders of magnitude, which offers a substantial advantage when measuring plutonium materials with large masses and high (α,n) neutron yields. In this work, a fast-neutron multiplicity counter is studied using the RMC (Reactor Monte Carlo code), independently developed at Tsinghua University. First, a function for outputting elastic-scattering timestamps was added to RMC, enabling the generation of complete time-pulse sequences. Then, the neutron multiplicity counting singles, doubles, and triples can be obtained. Second, the system of equations for fast-neutron multiplicity counting was investigated. Considering the differences between spontaneous-fission spectra and (α,n) spectra in PuO₂ materials, an improved set of fast-neutron multiplicity equations is proposed. Validation tests show that the improved equations enhance the accuracy of mass inversion to some extent, demonstrating the correctness and effectiveness of the method.

Keywords: Fast neutron multiplicity, point model equation, RMC, Liquid scintillation detectors

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutron Multiplicity Counting (NMC) is a type of non-destructive assay (NDA) method used for the analysis of special nuclear materials. NMC measures the time intervals between neutrons leaking from the surface of nuclear materials, analyzes the correlation information of neutrons in the fission chain, obtains the neutron multiplicity distribution, and determines the singles, doubles, and triples of neutron multiplicity counting. By solving the neutron multiplicity counting equations, the mass of the nuclear material can be inferred. Traditional neutron multiplicity counters require slowing down fission neutrons before they are captured by ³He, followed by time-sequence analysis of the fission neutron chain. Due to the scarcity of ³He, both homeland security and nuclear safeguards applications are actively seeking alternative neutron detectors to replace ³He tubes.

Fast Neutron Multiplicity Counters (FNMC), based on liquid scintillation detectors, offer excellent (n,γ) discrimination capability. These counters do not require neutron moderation and can directly detect fission neutrons emitted by nuclear materials. Fast-neutron detection provides substantial advantages because it preserves and measures the intrinsic nanosecond time scale of spontaneous and induced fission

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neutrons, rather than the microsecond scale resulting from neutron thermalization in thermal-neutron detectors. The neutron lifetime is shortened by up to three orders of magnitude, which is highly beneficial for measuring plutonium materials with large masses and high (α, n) neutron yields [1]. The University of Michigan (UM) has been conducting research since 2012 on Fast Neutron Multiplicity Counters (FNMC) based on liquid scintillators with (n, γ) discrimination capability. The University of Michigan has carried out extensive experimental investigations on fast neutron multiplicity counting systems, with a primary emphasis the EJ-309 series liquid scintillators. This research encompasses passive fast neutron multiplicity measurements as well as studies using the UNCL system [2, 3]. Furthermore, dedicated experiments were performed to evaluate and improve (n, γ) discrimination capabilities. In addition to experimental studies, the University of Michigan developed MCNPX-PoliMi based on MCNPX, which can be used for both thermal- and fast-neutron multiplicity counting analysis [3, 4]. Li et al, and Zhang et al developed fast neutron multiplicity counting capabilities based on Geant4 and conducted studies using BC501A liquid scintillation detectors [5, 6, 7]. They further proposed a correction method for the multiplication factor M , which led to a noticeable improvement in the accuracy of mass reconstruction [8]. It can be seen that fast neutron multiplicity counting remains both a prominent research focus and a challenging topic, and it also represents an area with significant potential for further development.

In this work, based on the independently developed Monte Carlo code RMC of Tsinghua University, we implemented an output module for elastic scattering events and developed a multiplicity shift register for fast neutron multiplicity counting [9, 10, 11]. This enabled the calculation of first-, second-, and third-order multiplicities, and, together with the fast neutron multiplicity counting equations, allowed for the reconstruction of nuclear material properties. During the study, it was further observed that the differences between (α, n) neutron spectra and the spontaneous fission spectrum of ^{240}Pu affect the traditional multiplicity equations. Accordingly, the equations were modified, leading to improved accuracy in the mass reconstruction results.

2. METHODS

The methodology consists of two components: the output of fast-neutron elastic scattering events and the point-model counting equations for fast neutron multiplicity analysis.

2.1. Fast neutron elastic scattering event record

Following the references, a detection system was constructed using RMC. The system consists of 24 liquid scintillation detectors arranged in three layers. Each layer is uniformly populated with BC501A liquid scintillators with a density of 0.874 g/cm^3 [12, 13, 14]. The geometric dimensions of each detector are $120 \text{ mm} \times 60 \text{ mm}$, and the detectors are positioned 20 cm from the central axis of the system. A detection threshold of 0.12 MeV (approximately one-third of Cs) was applied. A ^{240}Pu source was placed at the center. The PuO_2 sample was modeled as a cylinder with a density of 2.5 g/cm^3 and was composed of ^{240}Pu , ^{239}Pu , and ^{16}O with an atomic ratio of 0.2:0.8:2. The modeled experimental setup is shown in Figure 1.

When a neutron enters the liquid scintillator, it undergoes collisions with hydrogen or carbon nuclei. The resulting recoil protons or carbon ions excite and ionize the scintillation material, producing photons. These photons are collected by the photocathode of the photomultiplier tube (PMT), where the emitted photoelectrons are multiplied and amplified to generate an output signal. Figure 2 illustrates the models of neutron elastic scattering with hydrogen nuclei and carbon nuclei, respectively. The recoil energies of protons and carbon nuclei can be expressed by Eq 1, where E_p denotes the recoil proton energy and E_c denotes the recoil carbon nucleus energy.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the simulation device

Figure 2. Elastic scattering models of neutrons with H and C nuclei

$$\begin{cases} E_p = E \cos^2 \Psi \\ E_c = \frac{48E \cos^2 \beta}{169} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

To characterize the relationship between energy deposition in the liquid scintillator and its scintillation output, the detector response can be expressed in terms of the equivalent electron energy. A signal is recorded only when the equivalent electron energy exceeds the detection threshold; otherwise, no count is registered. The equivalent electron energy L_e and its functional relationship with the recoil proton energy E_p and the recoil carbon nucleus energy E_c are given in Eq. 2.

$$L_e = \begin{cases} 0.07269E_p + 0.11237E_p^2, E_p \leq 1.5 \\ -0.20570 + 0.35260E_p + 0.01343E_p^2 + 0.0025E_p^3, 1.5 < E_p \leq 3.5 \\ -0.25999 + 0.34141E_p + 0.03303E_p^2 - 0.00092E_p^3, 3.5 < E_p \leq 8 \\ -2.90980 + 0.87800E_p, E_p > 8 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$L_e = 0.02E_c$$

The overall process for obtaining fast neutron multiplicity counts is illustrated in Figure 3. First, the elastic scattering event times are recorded to generate a time-stamp sequence, which is then processed through a multiplicity shift register to obtain the fast neutron multiplicity counts.

2.2. Fast neutron point model equation

The fast neutron multiplicity counting equations are derived from the classical point-model formulation, in which the parameters to be determined are simplified to the spontaneous fission rate F , the multiplication factor M , and the (α, n) ratio coefficient α . By introducing the probability generating function (PGF) and employing the established mathematical model, the fast-neutron multiplicity measurement equations for plutonium materials were derived, as shown in Eq 3.

$$\begin{cases} S = F\varepsilon(1+k)v_{sf,1}(1+\alpha)M \\ D = \frac{F\varepsilon^2(1+k)^2f_dM^2}{2} \left[v_{sf,2} + \left(\frac{M-1}{v_{i1}-1} \right) v_{sf,1}(1+\alpha)v_{i2} \right] \\ \quad + F\varepsilon k f_d v_{sf,1}(1+\alpha)M \\ T = \frac{F\varepsilon^3(1+k)^3f_tM^3}{6} \left[\begin{aligned} &v_{sf,3} + \left(\frac{M-1}{v_{i1}-1} \right) 3v_{sf,2}v_{i2} \\ &+ \left(\frac{M-1}{v_{i1}-1} \right) v_{sf,1}(1+\alpha)v_{i3} \\ &+ 3 \left(\frac{M-1}{v_{i1}-1} \right)^2 v_{sf,1}(1+\alpha)v_{i2}^2 \end{aligned} \right] \\ \quad + F\varepsilon^2k(1+k)f_tM^2 \left[v_{sf,2} + \left(\frac{M-1}{v_{i1}-1} \right) v_{sf,1}(1+\alpha)v_{i2} \right] \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In Eq. 3, S , D , and T refer to the singles, doubles, and triples in neutron multiplicity counting, respectively. F denotes the spontaneous fission rate, ε represents the neutron detection efficiency, M is the leakage multiplication factor, α signifies the ratio of the neutron emission rate from (α, n) reactions to the spontaneous fission neutron emission rate, f_d stands for the double-gate fraction, and f_t denotes the triple-gate fraction, reflecting the proportion of the gate width G over the entire decay time. v_{ij} is the induced fission neutron multiplicity j th moment, and v_{sj} is the j th moment of the multiplicity of spontaneous fission neutrons. k is the crosstalk factor. By solving the system of three equations, the three unknowns F , M , and α can be determined, and the mass of spontaneous fission material can be calculated through F .

Figure 3. Simulation of fast neutron multiplicity counting process

The difference between the (α,n) neutron spectrum and the ^{240}Pu spontaneous fission spectrum is shown in the Figure 4. Therefore, considering this difference, the contributions of (α,n) neutrons and ^{240}Pu spontaneous fission neutrons to the multiplicity counting were separated, and the fast neutron multiplicity counting equations were rederived. The rederived set of equations is shown in Eq 4.

Figure 4. Neutron Energy Spectra of ^{240}Pu Spontaneous Fission and (α,n) Reactions

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} S = Fv_{sf,1}(\varepsilon_{sf}(1 + k_{sf}) + \varepsilon_{\alpha}\alpha(1 + k_{\alpha}))M \\ D = \frac{Ff_dM^2}{2} \left[\varepsilon_{sf}^2(1 + k_{sf})^2v_{sf,2} + \left(\frac{M-1}{v_{i1}-1} \right) v_{sf,1}(\varepsilon_{sf}^2(1 + k_{sf})^2 + \alpha\varepsilon_{\alpha}^2(1 + k_{\alpha})^2)v_{i2} \right] \\ \quad + Ff_dv_{sf,1}(k_{sf}\varepsilon_{sf} + \varepsilon_{\alpha}\alpha k_{\alpha})M \\ T = \frac{Ff_tM^3}{6} \left[\begin{array}{l} (1 + k_{sf})^3\varepsilon_{sf}^3v_{sf,3} + \left(\frac{M-1}{v_{i1}-1} \right) 3v_{sf,2}v_{i2}\varepsilon_{sf}^3(1 + k_{sf})^3 \\ + \left(\frac{M-1}{v_{i1}-1} \right) v_{sf,1}(\varepsilon_{sf}^3(1 + k_{sf})^3 + \varepsilon_{\alpha}^3\alpha(1 + k_{\alpha})^3)v_{i3} \\ + 3 \left(\frac{M-1}{v_{i1}-1} \right)^2 v_{sf,1}(\varepsilon_{sf}^3(1 + k_{sf})^3 + \varepsilon_{\alpha}^3\alpha(1 + k_{\alpha})^3)v_{i2}^2 \end{array} \right] \\ \quad + Ff_tM^2 \left[k_{sf}(1 + k_{sf})\varepsilon_{sf}^2v_{sf,2} + \left(\frac{M-1}{v_{i1}-1} \right) v_{sf,1}(k_{sf}(1 + k_{sf})\varepsilon_{sf}^2 + k_{\alpha}(1 + k_{\alpha})\varepsilon_{\alpha}^2\alpha)v_{i2} \right] \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

In Eq. 4, ε_{sf} is the detection efficiency of spontaneous fission sources, ε_{α} is the detection efficiency of (α,n) neutron sources, k_{sf} is the crosstalk factor of spontaneous fission sources and k_{α} is the crosstalk factor of (α,n) neutron sources. The other parameters have the same meanings as per Eq. 3.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, in order to obtain the detection efficiency ε and crosstalk factor k in Eq 3, the calibration was performed using ^{252}Cf . The detection efficiency and crosstalk factor calculated using ^{252}Cf were 15.52% and 8.33%, respectively.

In order to investigate the effectiveness of the modified fast neutron point-model equations, the mass inversion results of samples with different masses were tested. Samples with ^{240}Pu masses of 695.04g,

347.52g, 1201.03g, and 75.06g were selected for testing, and the singles, doubles, and triples were calculated for each of these four ^{240}Pu masses. Meanwhile, to solve the modified point model equations, it is necessary to obtain the detection efficiency and crosstalk factor for both the (α, n) source and the ^{240}Pu spontaneous fission source. The results are shown in Table I.

Table I. Counting and Parameter Calculation Results

^{240}Pu Mass	ϵ_{sf}	k_{sf}	ϵ_{α}	k_{α}	Singles	Doubles	Triples
695.04	14.97%	7.45‰	19.25%	6.04‰	164689.93	25717.14	4204.69
347.52	15.04%	7.31‰	19.50%	6.03‰	80994.04	11887.85	1756.16
1201.03	14.92%	7.54‰	18.98%	6.19‰	291445.86	49497.47	9342.24
75.06	15.12%	7.18‰	19.88%	5.82‰	16897.43	2191.38	260.02

Using the calculated parameters of the multiplicity counting equations together with the singles, doubles, and triples, Eq 3 and 4 were solved separately to obtain the mass inversion results and the corrected inversion results. The results are shown in Table II. From Table II, it can be seen that the accuracy of the corrected mass inversion results has improved compared with the uncorrected ones, demonstrating the validity of the proposed approach and method. Future work will focus on further optimising the fast neutron multiplicity counting equations to improve mass inversion accuracy.

Table II. Comparison of sample mass inversion results

^{240}Pu Mass	Uncorrected Results	Relative error	Corrected Results	Relative error
695.04	645.36	7.15%	658.39	5.27%
347.52	321.27	7.56%	325.88	6.23%
1201.03	1108.98	7.66%	1136.94	5.34%
75.06	68.79	8.36%	69.25	7.75%

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a fast neutron multiplicity counting platform based on liquid scintillator detectors was constructed using the Monte Carlo code RMC. An elastic scattering event output model was developed to generate time pulse sequences, from which the neutron multiplicity singles, doubles, and triples were obtained. The fast-neutron multiplicity counting equations were also examined, and considering the spectral differences between (α, n) neutrons and ^{240}Pu spontaneous fission neutrons, the equations were modified accordingly. Using the calculated singles, doubles, and triples for verification, the proposed method was shown to improve mass inversion accuracy. Future work will focus on further optimising the fast neutron multiplicity counting equations to achieve additional improvements in mass inversion accuracy.

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